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**Evaluating the Role of Christian Conflict
Management Practices in Building
Sustainable Peace in Nasarawa Eggon
Local Government Area, Nasarawa State,
Nigeria**

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Abstract

Conflict continues to pose a major challenge to peaceful coexistence and sustainable development in Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Persistent disputes arising from ethnic, political, religious, and socio-economic factors have often escalated into violence, resulting in loss of lives, destruction of property, and strained communal relations. This study evaluates the role of Christian conflict management practices in building sustainable peace within the area. Specifically, it examines the causes and dynamics of conflict in Nasarawa Eggon, identifies Christian-based conflict management practices employed by churches and Christian organizations, and assesses how biblical principles such as forgiveness, reconciliation, love, and dialogue influence peacebuilding processes. Adopting a qualitative

case study design, the study draws on oral interviews, historical analysis, and document review of relevant secondary sources. Purposive sampling was used to engage church leaders, clergy, Christian youth leaders, and community stakeholders involved in peace initiatives. Thematic analysis reveals that Christian conflict management practices contribute to enhanced mutual understanding, reduced hostility, and improved social cohesion, although their effectiveness is constrained by contextual challenges such as religious pluralism and limited institutional collaboration. The study concludes that Christian approaches represent a viable and complementary framework for sustainable peacebuilding in Nasarawa Eggon and recommends their integration into community leadership structures, local governance processes, and interfaith dialogue mechanisms to strengthen long-term peace and harmony.

Keywords: Christian Conflict Management, Faith-Based Mediation, Nasarawa Eggon, Peacebuilding, Sustainable Peace

Introduction

Conflict is an inevitable aspect of human interaction, often arising from differences in values, beliefs, and interests. However, within the Christian tradition, conflict is not merely viewed as destructive but also as an opportunity for growth, reconciliation, and the demonstration of godly virtues. The Christian approach to conflict management emphasizes forgiveness, reconciliation, peace-building, and the application of biblical principles in resolving disputes. The Scriptures consistently call for believers to seek peace and pursue it, as reflected in Paul's admonition, "If it is possible, as far as it depends on you, live at peace with everyone" (Holy Bible, Rom. 12.18). Scholars observe that Christianity places reconciliation at the center of conflict resolution, encouraging believers to imitate Christ's model of love and sacrifice (Augoye 2017). Similarly, theologians argue that forgiveness and dialogue remain the bedrock of Christian peacebuilding, fostering unity within communities (Gordon 2019). Thus, the Christian approach does not only address disputes but also seeks to restore relationships and promote communal harmony, making it a vital framework for sustainable conflict management. Christians are biblically conscripted to resolve conflict because it was the principle that was inculcated in them by Jesus Christ. It is on this account that Christians always sort for a means of living in peace with one another, settle dispute that if allowed to linger, it could lead to crises that may lead to destruction of lives and properties worth millions of naira, and put some people in perpetual trauma and

psychological unbalance in the society. Despite existing studies on faith-based conflict resolution and the broader role of religion in peacebuilding, there is limited empirical research that specifically explores how Christian conflict management practices operate at the grassroots level in local government contexts such as Nasarawa Eggon. Most available literature tends to focus on macro-level religious roles in peace processes (e.g., national or international contexts), often overlooking community-based Christian interventions and their measurable impact on sustainable peace in rural or semi-urban Nigerian settings. Furthermore, while general studies recognize the theoretical contributions of Christian doctrines such as forgiveness, reconciliation, and love to conflict transformation, there is a lack of localized, context-specific evidence demonstrating how these doctrinal principles are applied in practice by church leaders and congregations in Nasarawa Eggon and how effective they are in preventing relapse into conflict. Therefore, this study seeks to fill these gaps by providing contextualized empirical insights into Christian conflict management practices in Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area, assessing both their strengths and limitations in fostering long-term sustainable peace in the community.

Concept of Conflict

Coser defines conflict as “a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power, and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure, or eliminate their rivals” (Coser 1956). This definition emphasizes the competitive nature of conflict within social relations. Burton defines conflict as “a relationship between two or more parties who believe they have incompatible goals” (Burton 1990). He stresses the role of perception in the emergence of conflict. Galtung distinguishes conflict from direct violence, defining it as “an incompatibility of goals between two or more parties” (Galtung 1996). His approach links conflict with broader issues of structural violence and inequality. Lederach defines conflict as “a natural part of human relationships that arises when two or more parties differ in interests, values, or goals” (Lederach 1997). He emphasizes that conflict, though often destructive, also has constructive and transformative potential.

Conflict is a universal phenomenon that has attracted scholarly attention across disciplines such as sociology, political science, psychology, and religious studies. Generally, conflict refers to a situation in which two or

more parties perceive their interests, goals, or values as incompatible, leading to tension and confrontation. According to Coser, conflict is “a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power, and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure, or eliminate the rivals” (Coser 1956). This definition emphasizes the competitive and often destructive nature of conflict within human interaction. From a psychological perspective, conflict arises when individuals face incompatible needs, desires, or expectations. In this sense, conflict is not inherently negative but can serve as an opportunity for growth, negotiation, and improved understanding when managed constructively.

Other scholars highlight the structural dimensions of conflict. Johan Galtung distinguishes between “direct violence” and “structural violence,” arguing that societal arrangements that perpetuate inequality, oppression, and exclusion are themselves forms of conflict (Galtung 1996). This perspective widens the concept of conflict beyond personal disputes to include systemic issues such as poverty, discrimination, and gender-based violence.

Review of the Concept of Conflict

Conflict is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that affects human relationships, communities, and societal development. Scholars have conceptualized conflict in various ways, reflecting its diverse manifestations and underlying causes. Coser (1956) defines conflict as “a struggle over values and claims to scarce status, power, and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralize, injure, or eliminate their rivals,” emphasizing the competitive and often destructive nature of conflict within social interactions. Burton (1990) highlights the perceptual dimension of conflict, describing it as “a relationship between two or more parties who believe they have incompatible goals,” suggesting that conflict often arises from perceived rather than actual incompatibility. Galtung (1996) further distinguishes between direct and structural violence, framing conflict not only as interpersonal tension but also as systemic inequality and oppression embedded within societal structures. Lederach (1997) extends this understanding by emphasizing that conflict, though potentially destructive, is a natural and transformative aspect of human relationships that can create opportunities for reconciliation, dialogue, and social change.

Conflict is universal, but its specific causes and forms are context-dependent. In Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area, conflicts often stem from ethnic, religious, political, and socio-economic differences, including land disputes, competition for resources, and intergroup tensions. These conflicts can escalate into violence, threatening community cohesion, social stability, and sustainable development. Understanding conflict in this local context requires integrating both general theoretical perspectives and faith-based approaches that have shaped social relations in the area.

Christianity provides a framework for addressing conflict constructively. Biblical principles such as forgiveness, reconciliation, love, tolerance, and dialogue offer moral and practical guidance for resolving disputes without recourse to violence. Lederach (1997) notes that religious values, when properly engaged, can transform conflict into opportunities for healing and communal unity. Churches and Christian organizations in Nasarawa Eggon often play active roles in mediating disputes, fostering dialogue between conflicting parties, and promoting reconciliation within communities. By applying these faith-based principles, conflict can shift from a destructive force to a mechanism for building sustainable peace.

In the Nigerian and African context, studies have shown that Christian conflict management practices are particularly effective when integrated with local governance structures, traditional leadership, and interfaith initiatives (Okafor, 2015; Adegbite, 2018). These practices include community mediation programs, pastoral counseling, peace workshops, and collaborative prayer initiatives, which contribute to reducing hostility, restoring relationships, and encouraging social cohesion. This highlights the relevance of examining conflict not only as a theoretical concept but also as a lived reality, where faith-based interventions complement broader peacebuilding efforts.

From the foregoing, conflict can be understood as a dynamic and multidimensional process that reflects competing interests, values, and structural inequalities. While conflict may be destructive if left unmanaged, it also holds constructive potential when addressed through Christian conflict management strategies. By situating conflict within both local and faith-based frameworks, this study seeks to explore how churches and Christian organizations in Nasarawa Eggon can mediate disputes, foster reconciliation, and contribute to sustainable peace in the community.

History and Socio-Cultural Context of Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area

Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area (LGA) is one of thirteen LGAs in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, with its administrative headquarters in the town of Eggon. The LGA spans an area of 1,208 km² and had a population of 149,129 according to the 2006 census. It comprises several towns and districts, including Ende, Ginda, Alizaga, Arugbadu, Bakvano, Eggon, Sako, Umme, Agunji, Alogani, Arikpa, Ezzen, Wakama, Angbaku, Buba, Galle, Gbamze, Ogbagi, Wogan, and Ubbe. Historically, the Eggon people were administratively placed under Plateau Province during the colonial era and later became part of Benue-Plateau State following Nigeria's independence in 1960. The 1976 Local Government Reforms under General Murtala Mohammed's military government restructured local governance nationwide, promoting grassroots development and political participation. This reform laid the foundation for recognizing Eggonland as a distinct administrative unit (Aku) (Ayih, 1999).

Beyond administrative developments, Nasarawa Eggon is characterized by a diverse socio-cultural and ethnic composition, predominantly inhabited by the Eggon ethnic group alongside smaller minority communities. Traditional governance structures, such as the Council of Elders and local chieftaincies, historically regulated communal affairs, mediated disputes, and maintained social cohesion. These systems continue to influence local conflict resolution practices today. The region has also witnessed religious transformations, particularly with the introduction and spread of Christianity during the colonial and post-colonial periods. Churches and Christian organizations have become central to the social life of the community, offering spiritual guidance and serving as mediators during communal disputes. Christianity in Nasarawa Eggon has coexisted with indigenous beliefs and Islam, creating a pluralistic religious environment. Historically, Nasarawa Eggon has experienced conflicts arising from ethnic tensions, land disputes, political competition, and socio-economic inequalities. While these conflicts have occasionally escalated into violence, the presence of churches and faith-based organizations has contributed to efforts at reconciliation, dialogue, and peacebuilding. Such interventions highlight the role of Christian principles such as forgiveness, love, reconciliation, tolerance, and dialogue—in fostering harmony and mitigating disputes. The socio-economic landscape of the LGA,

predominantly agrarian with limited infrastructural development, has also shaped the patterns of local conflicts. Competition over land and resources, coupled with the interplay of ethnic and religious identities, has historically necessitated structured conflict management mechanisms. In this context, Christian conflict management practices are particularly significant, as they complement traditional and governmental approaches to sustaining peace and social cohesion. By situating the historical, socio-cultural, and religious development of Nasarawa Eggon within the framework of conflict and peacebuilding, this study establishes a contextual basis for examining the efficacy of Christian approaches to conflict management in fostering sustainable peace within the LGA.

Religious Practice in Nasarawa-Eggon.

Religion plays a central role in the social and cultural life of Nasarawa-Eggon Local Government Area (LGA). The LGA is home to diverse religious traditions, reflecting both indigenous beliefs and the impact of global religions.

Traditional Religion

The Eggon traditional religion remains an important aspect of cultural identity. Before the introduction of Christianity and Islam, the Eggon people practiced a religion (Lolo) centered on ancestral worship, rituals, and reverence for spiritual forces associated with nature. Central to this belief system is Ahogben (the Supreme Being) and divinities such as Angbashimu, which represent protective spirits and serve as mediators between humans and the divine (Blench 2015). Ritual festivals, sacrifices, and communal prayers are part of traditional worship, especially during planting and harvest seasons (Abimiku 2011).

Christianity

Christianity has grown to become the dominant religion in Nasarawa Eggon. Missionary activities during the colonial period, particularly by the Sudan United Mission (SUM) and the Roman Catholic Church, established strong Christian communities. Today, denominations such as Evangelical Reformed Church of Christ (ERCC), Evangelical Church Winning All (ECWA), Catholic Church, Anglican Communion, and Pentecostal movements are widespread. Christianity is deeply integrated into

community life, shaping education, moral and values (Katongole and Rice 2008).

Islam

Islam is also practiced in Nasarawa-Eggon, though it is less widespread compared to Christianity. Its presence is attributed to trade and migration of Hausa-Fulani communities into the area. Muslims in the LGA are mostly concentrated in mixed urban centers, where mosques and Islamic schools serve as focal points for religious practice (Mamman 1995).

Historical Overview of Conflict in Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area

Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area (LGA) of Nasarawa State is situated within Nigeria's Middle Belt, a region historically marked by ethnic plurality, religious diversity, and recurrent communal conflicts. Over time, socio-political competition, environmental pressures, and identity-based mobilization have combined to produce cycles of violence that continue to undermine peace and development. Understanding this historical trajectory is crucial for evaluating contemporary peacebuilding strategies, particularly faith-based interventions such as Christian conflict management practices. Historically, conflict in Nasarawa Eggon predates colonial rule. In the pre-colonial period, the Eggon people lived in decentralized clan-based settlements governed by elders and kinship networks. Disputes commonly arose over land boundaries, hunting territories, and access to water resources. While some conflicts escalated into violent confrontations, they were often resolved through indigenous mechanisms such as mediation by elders, compensation, oath-taking and strategic marriage alliances (Mamman 1995). These systems emphasized reconciliation and communal harmony, reflecting an early preference for restorative rather than punitive justice.

Colonial rule fundamentally altered these conflict patterns. The British administration introduced indirect rule and imposed a centralized chieftaincy system that disrupted the Eggon's traditionally autonomous clan structure. This restructuring generated resistance and rivalry among clans, many of which perceived the new system as an erosion of local authority and identity (Umbugala 2021). Furthermore, colonial taxation policies and the promotion of a cash-crop economy intensified competition over land, transforming it from a communal resource into a contested

economic asset. These changes laid the structural foundations for post-colonial conflicts by reshaping governance, land tenure, and economic relations (Blench 2015).

In the post-colonial period, conflicts in Nasarawa Eggon increasingly reflected Nigeria's broader ethno-political and religious struggles. The LGA is inhabited predominantly by the Eggon people, alongside other ethnic groups such as the Fulani, Gwandara, and Migili. While this diversity has enriched social life, it has also generated competition over political representation, access to land, and control of local resources. From the late twentieth century onward, the farmer–herder conflict emerged as a dominant source of violence. Sedentary Eggon farmers depend largely on agriculture, whereas Fulani pastoralists rely on open grazing. Population growth, environmental degradation, and climate change have intensified pressure on land and water resources, leading to frequent violent clashes when cattle destroy crops or grazing routes intersect with farmlands (Okoli and George 2014). These conflicts mirror wider Middle Belt tensions and have resulted in loss of lives, displacement, and deep-seated mistrust among communities.

A significant escalation in conflict occurred with the emergence of the Ombatse movement, an indigenous Eggon religious and cultural association that later evolved into a militant force. Ombatse became a vehicle for articulating grievances related to political marginalization, cultural domination, and perceived injustice within Nasarawa State. The crisis reached its peak in 2013 when clashes between Ombatse members and security forces in Alakyo led to the deaths of dozens of police officers, drawing national attention and intensifying communal suspicion (Human Rights Watch 2013). The Ombatse uprising illustrates how ethnic identity, religion, and political exclusion can intersect to produce violent conflict, further weakening trust between communities and state institutions.

Religious pluralism has also shaped conflict dynamics in Nasarawa Eggon. The population is divided among Christianity, Islam, and indigenous religious traditions. While this pluralism has the potential to foster mutual enrichment, it has at times become a source of rivalry, particularly when intertwined with political competition. Political elites have frequently been accused of exploiting ethnic and religious identities for electoral advantage, thereby deepening communal divisions and fueling violence (Maiangwa 2014). Disputes over indigene–settler status, access to economic

opportunities, and political inclusion further exacerbate tensions and sustain cycles of grievance and retaliation (Ishaq and Shousha 2021).

The consequences of these conflicts have been severe. Violent clashes have resulted in significant loss of lives and widespread displacement, while persistent insecurity has undermined agricultural production, the mainstay of the local economy. Once known for yam cultivation, parts of Nasarawa Eggon have experienced declining output as farmers abandon their fields due to fear and instability (Mba 2024). Conflict has also disrupted education, healthcare delivery, and infrastructural development, while eroding social trust and confidence in government institutions. These conditions have created a fragile social environment in which sustainable peace remains difficult to achieve.

This historical overview demonstrates that conflict in Nasarawa Eggon is not episodic but deeply rooted in structural, historical, and identity-related factors. Consequently, peacebuilding initiatives must address not only immediate security concerns but also the moral, relational, and social dimensions of conflict. It is within this context that Christian conflict management practices—emphasizing reconciliation, forgiveness, justice, dialogue, and community healing—have emerged as significant grassroots responses to violence. Situating Christian peace efforts within this historical landscape provides a critical foundation for evaluating their role and effectiveness in building sustainable peace in Nasarawa Eggon.

Historical Context and Methodology

Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area, in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, has long experienced recurrent conflicts shaped by ethnic diversity, religious pluralism, and political marginalization. Predominantly inhabited by the Eggon people alongside Fulani, Gwandara, and Migili communities, the area has been marked by farmer–herder disputes, identity-based mobilization, and contestation over land and political power (Blench, 2015; Okoli & George, 2014). Historical records indicate that pre-colonial disputes over land and resources were often mediated through diplomacy and marriage alliances (Mamman, 1995), while colonial and post-colonial centralization of authority intensified tensions (Umbugala, 2021). In contemporary times, the emergence of movements such as Ombatse and the interplay of religious differences have exacerbated social divisions,

undermining trust, development, and inter-communal cohesion (Human Rights Watch, 2013; Maiangwa, 2014).

Understanding this historical trajectory provides a foundation for evaluating Christian conflict management practices. Churches in Nasarawa Eggon engage in mediation, reconciliation, interfaith dialogue, and humanitarian support to reduce violence and foster social harmony. A qualitative case study design was adopted to explore these interventions in depth (Yin, 2018). The study is grounded in a multi-theoretical framework combining Conflict Transformation Theory, Structural-Functional Theory, Social Capital Theory, and a Biblical Peacebuilding perspective. This framework situates churches as stabilizing social institutions, highlights their role in building trust and cooperation, and explains the theological principles motivating forgiveness and reconciliation.

Participants were purposively selected and included clergy, lay leaders, youth and women's group coordinators, and community members involved in church-led peace initiatives (Patton, 2015). Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis to ensure triangulation and contextual validity. Thematic content analysis was employed to identify patterns and themes, which were interpreted in light of the theoretical framework (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, cultural sensitivity, and participant rights, were rigorously observed. Trustworthiness was enhanced through member checking, reflexivity, and thick description, ensuring the findings reliably reflect the lived experiences and practices of the community.

This integrated approach enables a contextually grounded, theory-informed evaluation of Christian conflict management in Nasarawa Eggon, linking historical causes and dynamics of conflict to practical, faith-based peacebuilding interventions and providing actionable insights for sustainable reconciliation and social cohesion.

Conclusion

Understanding the historical trajectory and structural dynamics of conflict in Nasarawa Eggon provides a necessary foundation for evaluating the role of Christian conflict management practices. By situating the analysis within the broader socio-political, ethnic, and religious context, the study ensures that the assessment of church-based interventions is both contextually

grounded and analytically robust. The historical overview highlights the complexity of conflict drivers, including farmer–herder disputes, identity-based mobilization, political marginalization, and religious pluralism, which require nuanced, multi-layered peace strategies. Against this backdrop, the study adopts a qualitative evaluative approach, examining how Christian institutions mediate disputes, foster reconciliation, promote interfaith dialogue, and engage in social and humanitarian interventions. This methodological orientation allows for a critical assessment of the effectiveness, limitations, and contextual relevance of Christian conflict management strategies, ensuring that conclusions and recommendations are not abstract prescriptions but empirically informed responses to historically and socially embedded conflict realities.

This study demonstrates that Christian approaches to conflict management constitute a significant grassroots contribution to peacebuilding in Nasarawa Eggon Local Government Area. Anchored in biblical principles of reconciliation, forgiveness, dialogue, and justice, Christian institutions provide both moral orientation and practical mechanisms for addressing disputes in a context shaped by protracted ethno-political tensions, religious pluralism, environmental stress, and historical grievances. Through mediation, counselling, peace education, interfaith engagement, and humanitarian support, churches have contributed to reducing hostility, rebuilding fractured social relations, and promoting nonviolent responses to conflict.

At the same time, the findings underscore that the effectiveness of Christian conflict management must be situated within the broader historical and structural realities of Nasarawa Eggon. Persistent farmer–herder conflicts, identity-based mobilization, political marginalization, and the enduring effects of the Ombatse crisis reveal that peace remains a negotiated and ongoing process rather than a definitive outcome. In this context, Christian peace initiatives function most effectively as complementary mechanisms that operate alongside traditional authorities, civil society organizations, and state institutions, rather than as standalone solutions to deeply rooted conflicts.

The study also identifies constraints that limit the transformative potential of Christian interventions, including inadequate resources, denominational fragmentation, perceptions of partiality, and the politicization of religious identity. Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing the

sustainability and credibility of faith-based peacebuilding efforts. Nonetheless, by framing peace not merely as the absence of violence but as a moral and social obligation grounded in justice, reconciliation, and communal well-being, the Christian perspective remains a relevant and constructive force within the fragile conflict landscape of Nasarawa Eggon.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and the historical context of conflict in Nasarawa Eggon, the study advances the following recommendations.

1. Sustained capacity building should be provided for clergy and lay leaders in conflict analysis, mediation, trauma healing, and peace psychology in order to enhance professionalism, impartiality, and effectiveness in responding to complex and identity-based conflicts.
2. Greater institutional commitment to interfaith collaboration is necessary, particularly through structured and continuous dialogue with Muslim and traditional religious leaders, given the plural religious environment and the historical politicization of religious identities in the area.
3. Churches should work in partnership with traditional rulers, women's groups, youth associations, and community-based organizations to support the formation of localized peace committees capable of functioning as early-warning and rapid-response mechanisms, especially in disputes related to land use and farmer–herder relations.
4. Peace education should be intentionally integrated into sermons, Bible studies, youth fellowships, and church-run educational institutions, with emphasis on nonviolence, reconciliation, tolerance, and respect for human dignity as long-term strategies for transforming conflict attitudes.
5. Closer collaboration between Christian institutions, government agencies, and civil society organizations is essential for addressing the structural drivers of conflict identified in this study, including land governance challenges, youth unemployment, and political exclusion, which lie beyond the capacity of religious actors alone.

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